

Intercropping with barley to improve winter pea production

Problem

Intercropping winter peas with barley could prevent legume canopy collapse and competition from weeds. There is limited knowledge, however, of the sowing ratios and agronomy that improve performance of winter pea-barley intercrops in Scotland.

Solution

We trialled multiple winter pea and barley cultivars in different sowing densities and ratios, soil cultivation, fertiliser and other inputs to detect the best outcomes for yield, weed and pest control.

Benefits

Highest grain yields and lowest weed cover were achieved with sowing densities of 1.25x standard densities (pea+barley), >50% std. density barley in the mix, and 75% of the standard nitrogen level for barley, indicating potential costs and benefits when maximizing winter pea performance.

Practical recommendations

- In Northern UK, winter legume-cereal crops can be sown within a suitable weather window in the autumn (September – November).
- Crops can be sown into ploughed or unploughed soil, although yields tend to be lower with direct drilled crops.
- Select varieties that are more likely to coincide in their maturity timings, using information from industry recommended lists of crop varieties.
- Winter survival and competitiveness of the main commercial pea varieties can be problematic but novel germplasm selected for intercropping offers improvements in future.
- Highest grain yields and lowest weed cover can be achieved with sowing densities of 1.25x standard densities (pea+barley), and 75% of the standard nitrogen level for barley (**Figure 1**).

Applicability box

Theme

Agronomy of legume-based intercrops

Keywords

Winter pea, winter barley, sowing density, ratio, nitrogen fertiliser, cultivation

Context

Scotland, rest of the UK

Application time

Autumn (sowing) to summer (harvest)

Required time

An annual crop growing season

Period of impact

An annual growing season

Equipment

Drills and combines capable of handling cereal and legume seeds and crops together, and grain separators

Best in

Arable cropping

Winter pea-barley crop trialled at the James Hutton Institute (Alison Karley).

Figure 1. Grain yield of pea+barley from a standard plot (6 m²) averaged across three years of field trials (nine in total) in Scotland, UK. Average yield varied in response to total intercrop sowing density (left – as a proportion of standard monocrop sowing density) and nitrogen fertiliser input level (right – as a percentage of standard winter barley N fertiliser levels).

- Pre-emergence herbicide reduces early weed competition but is rarely needed after crop establishment; protection of the pea crop against bird damage can be important for crop establishment.
- Split fertiliser treatments are applied at sowing (Sept-Nov) and during barley tillering (March-May), at 50-75% of the standard nitrogen rate for barley.
- Monitor crop development, and pest and disease incidence, although the latter was low in our 3 years of trials.
- Crops are combine harvested in late summer (Aug-Sept); desiccation might be needed prior to harvest if pea and barley do not converge in maturity timing.
- Pea and barley grain can be separated after harvest, depending on access to grain drying, storage and separating facilities.

Further information

Video

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jiB79tr2pXA&t=4s>

Weblinks

For more practical recommendations, see:

- <https://www.arablescotland.org.uk/virtual-event-2020>
- <https://www.arablescotland.org.uk/virtual-event-2021>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KLwdlpzFRm8>

About this practice abstract

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Project website: www.legumesproject.eu

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